

SHORT NOTES

On the Oxycarbonate of Thorium

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In the literature there are conflicting reports¹⁻³ regarding the composition and carbonate content of the gelatinous precipitate obtained when a thorium salt solution is treated with an equivalent amount of sodium carbonate solution. The present note describes the results of a thermogravimetric study of this product, called in the literature thorium oxycarbonate, and given the formula, $\text{ThOCO}_3 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

For this study the precipitate was obtained by treating a 0.2M-Th(NO₃)₄ solution with twice its volume of 0.2M-Na₂CO₃ solution. The freshly precipitated material after filtration, single washing, and drying on a water bath at about 60° had a composition very nearly corresponding to $\text{ThOCO}_3 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

TABLE I

	ThO ₂ .	CO ₂ .	H ₂ O.	Loss on ignition.
Found (%)	.. 77.60	11.90	10.50	22.40
Calc. (%)	.. 76.75	12.79	10.46	23.25

It was observed that the CO₂ content decreased on repeated washing or on digestion with hot water. The thermogravimetric analysis was carried out on a Stanton recording thermobalance of 1 mg. sensitivity, using heating rates of 8° and 2°/min. The thermogravimetric curves showed a continuous decomposition with no definitely marked step as is obtained for normal carbonates. Decomposition was somewhat rapid at the start and then attained a constant rate to about 350°, when the loss was 18% and corresponded to 1 molecule each of H₂O and CO₂. The substance on further heating lost only H₂O to 500° when a residue of ThO₂ was obtained. It was confirmed by (i) mass spectroscopic analysis that the gases escaping before 350° were a mixture of H₂O and CO₂, (ii) chemical analysis that the residue at 350° contained no CO₂, and (iii) X-ray diffraction that the residue at 500° and above was ThO₂.

From these results it is concluded that the CO₂ is not attached as the CO₃²⁻ ion to thorium, but is present only as weakly attached molecular CO₂ to the thorium hydroxide or the hydrated oxide, thus Th(OH)₄CO₂ or ThO₂·2H₂O·CO₂. The latter possibility is not considered likely because (i) the precipitate is gelatinous, (ii) it has no X-ray diffraction pattern, (iii) the oxide does not form directly, and (iv) the residue at 350° is

1. Chydonius, *Pogg. Ann.*, 1868, 119, 43.2. Cleve, *Bull. Soc. chim.*, 1874, 21, 115.3. *Compt. rend.*, 1911, 153, 66.

amorphous and more like the hydroxide. It is very likely, on the other hand, that there might be the formation of a bicarbonate species due to the interaction of the OH and CO₂. Thus it is considered that the formula of the precipitates could be best represented as either Th(OH)₄.CO₂ or Th(OH)₃.HCO₃.

The thermolysis of this precipitate is analogous to the dehydration of Th(OH)₄; only in the early stages the relatively loosely held CO₂ is also simultaneously lost. The decomposition products at various intermittent temperatures have been assigned specific formulas by Chauvenet³ and are reported in Gmelin⁴. It is considered that these decomposition products do not represent specific compounds but are merely transient states in the continuous decomposition of Th(OH)₄.CO₂. All of these decomposition products could be represented by a general formula Th(OH)_{4-x}.O_{x/2}(1-y)CO₂ where x and y can take any value between 0 and 4, and 0 and 1 respectively. Thus at the beginning x and y are zero and the compound is Th(OH)₄.CO₂; at 350° x = 2 and y = 1 and the compound is ThO(OH)₂; at 500°, x = 4 and the compound is ThO₂, all other intermediate formulas would be possible.

The authors thank Shri M. R. Ghate for the mass spectroscopic analysis.

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Received October 18, 1962.

4. "Handbuch der anorganischen Chemie", Vol. 44, p. 301.